

Artificial Intelligence, Change Leadership, and Employee Performance: Evidence from BUMN KCPs in Surakarta

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ABSTRACT: In the era of digital transformation, the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the banking industry presents opportunities to increase efficiency as well as challenges in the form of concerns about the replacement of human roles by technology. This condition has the potential to affect employee performance and work attachment if not managed properly. This study aims to analyze the influence of Artificial Intelligence on Employee Performance and Job Attachment, as well as test the role of Change Leadership as a moderation variable in the context of state-owned banking. The quantitative approach was used by collecting data through a Google Form-based questionnaire which was distributed online and offline to 225 employees from 12 sub-branch offices of state-owned banks in the city of Surakarta. Respondents were selected using the probability cluster sampling technique. Data analysis was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling method based on Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). The results of the study show that Artificial Intelligence has a positive but not significant effect on Employee Performance and Work Attachment. Then, the role of Change Leadership was found to be able to strengthen the influence of Artificial Intelligence on Employee Performance and Work Attachment, which emphasizes the importance of adaptive leadership in managing technological change. Theoretically, these findings enrich the perspective of Dynamic Capabilities theory by showing that the synergy between technology and change leadership shapes the ability of organizations to adapt in a digital environment. Practically, this research provides implications for the banking industry in optimizing the use of AI through adaptive leadership to improve employee performance and engagement in a sustainable manner.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence, Change Leadership, Employee Performance, Work Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

Many facets of life have seen significant changes as a result of the advancement of information technology during the fourth industrial revolution. One of the technologies that can mimic human intellect is artificial intelligence (AI), which is the primary force behind innovation and is utilized extensively in services (Koay & Muthuveloo, 2021).

AI's significance is unavoidable. According to McKinsey's 2022 analysis of the state of artificial intelligence, the banking sector leads the way in using AI to create digital goods and services (Ahdia, 2023). AI is increasingly used in routine banking tasks like fraud detection, transaction analysis, and surveillance (Wibowo, 2024). However, employees are also significantly impacted by the constant use of AI. Global banks may lay off 200,000 workers in the next three to five years, according to Bloomberg Intelligence (BI). This could lead to workplace anxiety and a lack of focus, which would lower employee performance (Ashri, 2025).

This phenomenon is becoming more and more significant in the city of Surakarta, which is now recognized as a target for investors in the development of AI technology due to its infrastructure, 5G networks, qualified digital talent, and facilities such as the AI Experience Center at Solo Techno Park, which provides education and technological demonstrations to the community and various industries (Espos.id, 2024). This facility's existence is consistent with banks' growing use of AI, particularly state-owned banks—that is, businesses in which the Central Government of the Republic of Indonesia owns the majority or all of their shares (Kumparan.com, 2024). Similar benefits are enjoyed by Surakarta City's state-owned banks, which also use AI in their operations. An AI-based credit scoring system that can evaluate the viability of prospective clients and swiftly and precisely trace the history of credit contracts or legal help is one example of how technology is utilized to increase operational efficiency and service accuracy (Saputra, 2025).

Even Nevertheless, it has been demonstrated that using AI can benefit businesses greatly by increasing worker engagement and performance (Malik, 2024). This technology is still a contentious issue for both practitioners and scholars. According to Reilly

(2018), the use of AI in academia can enhance human resource functioning, but there are hazards associated with skills gaps because certain employees lack the abilities needed to use the technology, which can impair worker performance and reduce work attachment. According to research by Wijayati et al. (2022), AI significantly and favorably affects worker engagement and performance. AI serves as a supporting tool by providing a range of choices, advantages, and services that can improve workers' capacity to finish jobs and boost engagement. However, AI's effects aren't always favorable. According to Koo et al. (2021), workers may become less attached to their jobs as a result of automation if they believe their duties and skills are obsolete. Critical thinking abilities in problem solving may be diminished by an excessive dependence on technology (Limna, 2023). Employee performance may suffer when routine jobs are replaced by the system, which limits their ability to hone their analytical abilities. According to research by Molla (2024), bank workers who perform a large percentage of repetitive operations typically have a negative opinion of AI because they believe that technology would eventually replace them. Concerns regarding employees' roles within the company are heightened by this situation, which may eventually have an impact on the caliber of employee performance and job attachment.

Conversely, for practitioners, the results According to the Upwork Research Institute, the use of AI may reduce worker productivity. According to the poll, which included 2,500 employees from the US, UK, Canada, and Australia, 96% of workers think AI can boost productivity, but 77% think it actually makes work harder because of rising demands and inadequate training. As a result, it may lower employee engagement, have an impact on performance, and raise the likelihood that workers would quit within the next six months (Scott, 2024). The results of preliminary interviews that researchers performed with staff members of state-owned banks in Surakarta supported the conclusions. Employee impressions of work connection and performance are examined in the interview. According to the findings, 90% of workers believed that the introduction of AI could lower performance and job attachment because workers are unable to adjust and fear that technology will replace them in their current position. Some workers experience a decline in work attachment as a result of this situation because they feel less engaged in the work process. Up to 10% of workers, however, believe that AI is a tool that genuinely facilitates task completion and boosts productivity. Employee trust in the company may decline if these changes are not accompanied by open communication, employee involvement, and future role certainty. Consequently, it will impair the work ethic and performance of state-owned bank workers in Surakarta.

Therefore, in order to handle employee concerns, establish trust, and offer assistance and training so that employees can play an optimal role during the digitization process, a leadership role—specifically change leadership—is required (Wijayati et al., 2022). Bhatt (2022) highlights that there is still a dearth of research on the moderating function of leadership in the relationship between the use of AI and employee performance and work attachment. The findings of earlier research's contradictions indicate that further investigation into this topic is still necessary.

There are currently few empirical studies that integrate AI, employee performance, work engagement, and the function of change leadership moderation, despite the fact that AI has emerged as a key force behind the banking industry's transformation. The results of earlier research have not accurately reflected the dynamics of AI application and its influence on employee behavior in various geographic contexts and organizational features because they have mostly concentrated on banking employees in the East Java region. Because of this, there is still a lack of knowledge on the complete relationship between AI, worker performance, and work attachment in the context of Surakarta City's state-owned banks. Thus, by examining the impact of AI on worker performance and work attachment and evaluating the function of change leadership as a moderating variable, this study seeks to close this gap.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Dynamic capabilities Theory*

The ability of a business to integrate, grow, and reorganize internal and external competences in order to react to and handle quick and changing environmental changes is known as dynamic capabilities theory, which was created by Teece & Pisano in 1994. According to this theory, internal competence encompasses all skills, procedures, and resources that come from within the company, including change leadership, employee performance, and work attachment. Conversely, the ability of the company to take advantage of opportunities and react to external environmental hazards is known as external competence (Teece et al., 2009). For instance, artificial intelligence was once a technology that was included from outside the company. Nonetheless, AI can become a component of internal competences that boost a business's competitiveness if it is effectively integrated into daily operations. Dynamic capabilities have been shown to be essential for the organization's sustainability, particularly in the face of an uncertain business climate. They also help to improve engagement and

performance at work. According to Konopik et al. (2022), an organization's ability to reorganize business processes and manage interactions with numerous stakeholders is just as important to its competitive advantage as its adoption of new technologies. In this situation, change leadership must be able to guide and guarantee the successful deployment of AI. An organization's ability to coordinate resources to create dynamic, adaptable capabilities and promote long-term growth determines its existence.

B. Artificial Intelligence

According to Wijayati et al. (2022), artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology that mimics human cognitive abilities to do tasks autonomously and without complete reliance on humans. According to Poola (2017), artificial intelligence is the creation of sophisticated systems that can outperform humans in a variety of domains. According to Chen et al. (2020), artificial intelligence (AI) is the study of how robots can be made to react intelligently to specific actions and possess learning capacities similar to those of humans. According to Abdallah et al. (2025), the use of AI is demonstrated by its capacity to efficiently manage data, optimize workflows, and offer the best possible assistance in decision-making.

C. Change Leadership

According to Ghavifekr and Adewale (2019), change leadership is the capacity of a leader to inspire and encourage others by means of a clear vision, a strong sense of drive, and the availability of resources to establish a strong basis for the implementation of change. According to Herald et al. (2008), shift leadership It is demonstrated by leadership conduct that offers high-quality change information, promotes proactive employee involvement, conveys changes in an understandable and transparent manner, and gives every employee the chance to participate in the change process.

D. Employee Performance

One of the most crucial objectives for any person or business is to perform at a better level. Employee performance, according to Biswakarma & Subedi (2024), is the outcome of an employee's labor and indicates how successfully or flawlessly the employee has fulfilled their duties and responsibilities. According to Na-Nan et al. (2018), employee performance is defined as the outcome of actions or work behaviors carried out by individuals in carrying out their duties with the aim of achieving results according to organizational expectations measured in terms of quality, quantity, and timeliness of work completion.

E. Work Engagement

According to Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), work attachment is a favorable psychological state associated with one's job that is assessed by a person's level of passion, commitment, and engagement. According to Bakker & Demerouti (2007), when workers find personal purpose and motivation, receive encouraging interpersonal support, and operate in a productive setting, they will feel obligated to work (Srivastava, 2008).

F. Relationship of Artificial Intelligence and Employee Performance

Even though it has been extensively debated throughout the years, the connection between technology and performance is still a hot topic. According to Malik et al. (2022), the use of AI can promote innovation and creativity and, in general, can lead to better worker performance. Learn More According to Bag et al. (2022), an organization's capacity to manage human resources strategically and adaptably to the dynamics of the business environment can be strengthened by a sustainable technology system, which will have a positive and significant impact on employee performance. According to Chin et al. (2024), AI and worker performance are positively and significantly correlated. Technology-based learning and development platforms are one way AI has contributed. These platforms have been shown to be successful in promoting skill development, which in turn has an effect on raising employee performance (Chowdhury et al., 2023).

H1. Artificial Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

G. Relationship of Artificial Intelligence and Work Engagement

Because AI has a significant impact on work processes and tasks, it has a wide-ranging effect on human labor (Rick et al., 2024). By providing organized guidance, monitoring, and rewards, AI systems can encourage employees to be actively involved in their work (Hughes et al., 2019). According to Toth et al. (2021), a number of studies have investigated the

possible use of AI in human resources, where it has been demonstrated to be able to considerably and favorably boost work attachment. AI can be included into performance management and hiring, among other HR tasks. Additionally, AI can help staff become more attached to their jobs and enhance their capacity to provide clients with timely, accurate, and reliable service (Prentice et al., 2023).

H2. Artificial Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Work Attachment.

H. Change Leadership moderates the effect of Artificial Intelligence on Employee Performance and Work Engagement

Other factors can either improve or diminish the association between AI and work attachment and employee performance (Wijayati et al., 2022). One psychological process thought to be able to control the relationship is change leadership. The capacity of leaders to guide, mold, and assist staff members in being prepared to successfully execute change is known as "change leadership" (Engida et al., 2022). Leadership is essential to the successful implementation of AI. To establish a work environment that is flexible, cooperative, and prepared to handle the difficulties of change, leadership support for staff members is crucial (Venugopal et al., 2024). According to Wijayati et al. (2022), change leadership has been shown to improve the correlation between AI implementation and worker performance and attachment to their jobs. Visionary leaders that are adept at utilizing technology foster a collaborative workplace, which boosts employee engagement and enhances overall performance. According to Belsito & Reutzler (2020), change leadership has been shown to be crucial in raising worker performance. Additionally, Hughes et al. (2019) state that it can boost work engagement by giving leaders guidance, keeping an eye on them, and rewarding them during the AI deployment process.

H3. Change leadership moderates the influence of AI on employee performance.

H4. Change leadership moderates the influence of AI on work engagement.

I. Research Thinking Framework

This study is a replication of Wijayati et al. (2022), which highlights the role of leadership and the significance of technology in enhancing employee outcomes. When compared to earlier studies, this one exhibits notable innovation in terms of the research object and its contextual relevance. In contrast to the prior research environment, this study focuses on state-owned bank employees in Surakarta City, who have distinct organizational traits, laws, and degrees of technology usage. By positioning artificial intelligence as an external skill that can be transformed into an internal organizational competency and change leadership as a managerial technique that facilitates the successful adaption process, the study further develops the Dynamic Capabilities Theory. Employee performance and work attachment are viewed in this paradigm as internal capabilities that demonstrate how well the company has aligned its human resources and technology. Therefore, it is anticipated that this study will contribute to the body of knowledge concerning the use of artificial intelligence to enhance employee performance and work attachment, which is influenced by change leadership, and offer more empirical support for the validity of the relationship between variables in the context of state-owned banking in the city of Surakarta.

Figure 2. Research Concept Model

Sources: Wijayati et al., (2022)

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a cross-sectional design and a quantitative methodology. The study is to explore the function of Change Leadership as a moderating variable and investigate the effects of Artificial Intelligence on Work Engagement and Employee Performance. Individuals, namely workers at the KCP (Auxiliary Branch Office) of state-owned banks in Surakarta, serve as the study's unit of analysis. All 1,289 workers from the 54 KCP state-owned banks in Surakarta City—Bank Mandiri, BRI, BNI, BTN, and BSI—are included in the research population (OJK Surakarta, 2025).

Because personnel were dispersed over multiple branches and locations, probability cluster sampling was used to determine the sample. By using this method, researchers can choose multiple KCPs at random to form clusters, totaling 12 offices. The KCP of state-owned banks was selected as the cluster's foundation because, although the number of employees in branch offices (KC) is significantly higher than that of KCPs, it does not satisfy one of the requirements of cluster sampling. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2013), the study's cluster sample characteristics include homogeneity between clusters, or groups that share comparable traits, such as each bank having a comparatively similar work system and job services. Next, heterogeneity in clusters refers to the fact that groupings have a variety of traits, such as variations in occupations and educational backgrounds. According to Hair et al. (2017), the number of samples required ranges from 150 to 300 respondents, as the minimum sample size is 5–10 times the number of indicators (30 indicators). 240 participants in this study received questionnaires. The remaining 15 surveys did not satisfy the requirements for data processing, whereas 225 of these were redeclared and qualified for processing. As a result, the sample size requirements were satisfied and the number of respondents used in this study is regarded as representative. KCP workers of state-owned banks in Surakarta were given online and offline questionnaires via social media platforms like email, Instagram, and WhatsApp, as well as in-person visits to the office following authorization. A 5-point Likert scale (1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree) was employed in the research tool. Instruments modified from earlier studies were used to measure the research variables: Artificial Intelligence Work Attachment 9 items Schaufeli & Bakker (2004), Employee Performance 7 items Na-Nan et al. (2018), Change Leadership 7 items Herold et al. (2008), and 7 items modified by Paschen et al. (2019). SmartPLS software was used to analyze the data using Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). Testing the measurement model (outer model) to evaluate the validity and reliability test is the first of two processes in the analysis stage. There are a number of tests, including the Goodness of Fit Model, a hypothesis test that uses t-statistics and t-table values, and structural model testing (inner model). This method enables researchers to evaluate the model's overall strength and confirm the direct relationship and moderation between variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigates the factors that affect employee performance and work attachment by highlighting Artificial Intelligence, and the role of change leadership (as moderation). This study involved 225 employees of KCP state-owned banks in Surakarta City who were involved in the use of AI-based systems in daily work activities. This study presents the demographic profiles of the respondents: age range <20 years (4.0%), 21–25 years (38.6%), 26–30 years (35.6%), >31 years (21.8%). Gender female (52.0%), male (48.0%). The last education is high school (13.9%), D3 (31.2%), S1 (46.5%), S2 (8.4%). Tenure <1 year (15.8%), 1–5 years (47.5%), 6–10 years (32.7%), >10 years (4.0%). The bank where BRI works (37.6%), Bank Mandiri (30.7%), BNI (22.8%), BSI (5.9%), BTN (3.0%). This demographic reflects a diverse sample and strongly represents the characteristics of employees who work at the KCP of state-owned banks in the city of Surakarta.

As the initial stage of testing in PLS-SEM, the Outer Model requires testing the validity and reliability of all questionnaire items (Hair et al., 2021). The validity test is used to assess whether or not a questionnaire is valid. As shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Requirement	Results
Artificial Intelligence	AI1	0.756	> 0.7 (Values in the range of 0.50–0.60 are still acceptable)	Valid
	FW2	0.758		Valid
	FW3	0.594		Valid
	FW4	0.860		Valid
	FW5	0.777		Valid

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Requirement	Results
Change Leadership	FW6	0.636		Valid
	FW7	0.788		Valid
	CL1	0.852	> 0.7 (Values in the range of 0.50–0.60 are still acceptable)	Valid
	CL2	0.817		Valid
	CL3	0.833		Valid
	CL4	0.813		Valid
	CL5	0.809		Valid
CL6	0.829	Valid		
CL7	0.830	Valid		
Employee Performance	EP1	0.800	> 0.7 (Values in the range of 0.50–0.60 are still acceptable)	Valid
	EP2	0.777		Valid
	EP3	0.842		Valid
	EP4	0.827		Valid
	EP5	0.774		Valid
	EP6	0.819		Valid
	EP7	0.851		Valid
Work Engagement	WE1	0.737	> 0.7 (Values in the range of 0.50–0.60 are still acceptable)	Valid
	WE2	0.756		Valid
	WE3	0.714		Valid
	WE4	0.739		Valid
	WE5	0.763		Valid
	WE6	0.755		Valid
	WE7	0.743		Valid
	WE8	0.770		Valid
	WE9	0.765		Valid

Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

The table above shows the results of the validity test with all measurement items having an Outer Loading value of >0.7. However, there are two indicators that have an outer loading value below 0.7, but are still maintained because they are still in the range of 0.50 – 0.60 which according to Hair et al., (2014) is still acceptable in exploratory research. This value shows that all indicators in the variable are able to be explained well by each of the indicators or can be said to be valid.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Requirement	Composite (rho_c)	Reliability Requirement	Results
Artificial Intelligence	0.893	>0.6	0.895	>0,70	Reliable
Change Leadership					
Employee Performance	0.923		0.938		Reliable
Work Engagement	0.915		0.932		Reliable
	0.903		0.920		Reliable

Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

Reliability Test is used to assess the strength and accuracy of measurement instruments (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Construct reliability has used Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. Table 2. indicates that the Composite Reliability result has a value of >0.7, meaning that it is considered superior for estimating the internal consistency of the construct. Furthermore, Cronbach's Alpha results have a value of >0.6 (Hair et al., 2017). Thus, all constructs are declared reliable and consistent.

Figure 2. Output Model Diagram
 Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

A conceptual model that explains the connection between Work Engagement (WE), Employee Performance (EP), Change Leadership (CL), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) within a research framework is shown in Figure 2. AI is positioned as the primary external factor influencing employee work outcomes, including engagement and performance. A variety of indicators that represent the aspects of employee behavior, attitudes, and views of leadership and technology use within the company are used to measure each construct. The arrangement of these indicators demonstrates how each construct is viewed as a latent variable that is represented empirically rather than directly measured.

This model illustrates the function of Change Leadership as a moderating variable in the relationship between AI and employee performance and job engagement in addition to direct interactions. This demonstrates that the context of leadership and change management practices used by the company have a significant impact on how technology affects workers. The process of employees adjusting to new technology is guided by change leadership, which also increases acceptance and reduces resistance to change. In general, the interdependencies among the variables in this model create a network that serves as the foundation for determining how well the model captures the phenomenon under investigation through the Goodness of Fit assessment.

Table 3. Inner Model Evaluation

Variable	R Square	Q Square
Employee Performance	0.337	0.217
Work Engagement	0.252	0.134

Source: Processed primary data, 2025

Table 4. Goodness of Fit Index

GOF Index	Results
$GoF = \sqrt{(AVE \times R^2)}$	0.00 – 0.24 subcategory
	0.25 – 0.37 medium category
	0.38 – 1.00 Category Tinggi
$GoF = \sqrt{(0.615 \times 0.08642)}$ $= \sqrt{0.231}$	Medium Fit

Source: Processed primary data, 2025

Based on the results of the calculation in Table 4. obtained a Goodness of Fit (GoF) value of 0.231. Referring to the criteria put forward by Tenenhaus et al. (2004), the range of GoF values is classified into three categories, namely 0.00–0.24 (small), 0.25–0.37 (medium), and 0.38–1.00 (high). Thus, the GoF value of 0.231 is in the small category according to the reference. These results show that the overall level of model fit is still relatively low, both in terms of measurement models and structural models. This means that the model's ability to explain the relationship between latent constructs and their indicators, as well as in explaining the relationships between constructs in structural models, is not optimal according to the GoF classification.

However, according to Tenenhaus et al. (2004) stated that GoF was proposed as an "operational solution" to provide a global measure of the PLS-SEM model, which suggests that GoF can be used to comprehensively evaluate the model even if it is low in value (Tenenhaus et al., 2004). In this context, low GoF values are still acceptable and still indicate a viable model for use, especially when combined with other evidence such as convergent validity, construct reliability, and adequate R² and Q² values as indicators of predictive strength and theoretical relevance of the model.

After ensuring that the model is reliable, a hypothesis test is carried out. Hypothesis testing by looking at the calculated value of the Path Coefficient on the inner model test. The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t-statistical value > 1.96 (α 5%) which means that if the t-statistical value of each hypothesis is greater than the p-value, it can be declared acceptable. The model includes artificial intelligence, employee performance, work attachment and change leadership (as moderation). The hypothesis test carried out in this study can be seen in two parts, namely the direct effect and the indirect effect.

Table 5. Results of Direct Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-value	Results
H1. Artificial Intelligence → Employee Performance	0.249	1.496	0.135	Positive but not statistically significant
H2. Artificial Intelligence → Work Engagement	0.253	1.549	0.121	Positive but not statistically significant

Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

The results of the hypothesis test as presented in Table 5. H1. AI has a positive effect on employee performance is declared unsupported. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficients were positive (0.235), statistical t (1.496), and p-value of 0.135, which means that they do not meet the significance criteria. These results mean that the application of AI has not been able to make a significant contribution to improving employee performance. This means that the high and low application of AI does not have an impact on improving employee performance. This is in line with Raisch, (2021), which states that AI does not automatically improve individual performance if it is not accompanied by clear changes in work processes and human roles. In the KCP of state-owned banks in Surakarta City, this condition can be understood because the implementation of AI generally still focuses on administrative aspects and standard services, such as data processing, risk assessment, or customer service support, while employee performance indicators still refer to operational targets and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which are standard and must be met. As a result, while AI aids work efficiency, its contribution to improving individual performance is not significantly reflected in formal performance assessments. Lunzaga *et al.*, (2025), also found that AI implementation is unlikely to have a significant impact on employee performance. Next, H2. Artificial intelligence has a positive but insignificant effect on work attachment. This is

evidenced by the positive path coefficients (0.253), t statistic (1.549), and p-value 0.121. This means that AI has not been able to build work attachment because attachment is psychological and relational, while the application of AI touches more on the technical and procedural aspects of work. This is supported Vodiškar & Ruiner, (2025) confirms that AI tends to improve task efficiency, but it does not necessarily increase employees' emotional and cognitive attachment to their work. In line with Rick et al., (2024) who found that the use of AI-based systems did not directly increase work engagement. At the KCP of state-owned banks in Surakarta City, the application of AI is generally still top-down and oriented towards service efficiency and compliance with regulations, such as automating transaction processes, reporting, and customer service. This condition causes employees to continue to work in a relatively rigid work pattern with limited autonomy, so the existence of AI has not been able to significantly increase the sense of attachment to work. In line with Dynamic Capability Theory, work attachment is not only determined by the availability of technology, but also by the organization's ability to reconfigure work processes and roles so that AI is perceived as an opportunity for self-development, competency enhancement, and employee empowerment, not just an automation tool.

Table 6. Results of Indirect Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-value	Results
H3. Change Leadership x Artificial Intelligence → Employee Performance	0.295	3.476	0.001	Significantly positive
H4. Change Leadership x Artificial Intelligence → Work Engagement	0.289	3.383	0.001	Significantly positive

Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

Test moderation as presented in Table 6. H4. Change Leadership moderates the influence of AI on employee performance is stated to be supported. Based on the results of the analysis, a statistical t-value of (3.476) with a p-value of 0.001, and a positive path coefficients (0.295) showed that moderation was accepted. This finding is supported by Wijayati et al., (2022), change leadership strengthens the influence of AI application on employee performance. This shows that visionary and development-oriented change leadership can strengthen the influence of AI on employee performance. According to Belsito & Reutzler, (2020) Change leadership has been proven to play a role as a strength or driver in improving employee performance. Next, H4. Change leadership moderates the influence of AI on work engagement by having a statistic t-value of (3.383), a p-value of 0.001, and a positive path coefficients (0.289). This means that the more effective the role of change leadership, the more impactful the application of AI will be in increasing work engagement. In the KCP environment of state-owned banks in Surakarta City which tends to be hierarchical and oriented towards regulatory compliance, the role of change leadership is crucial to create a sense of security, trust, and attachment for employees during the transformation process. With strong change leadership support, AI can increase employee engagement in a sustainable manner. These results indicate that change leadership plays an important role in strengthening the application of AI to work attachment, because active and adaptive leadership is able to integrate AI into the work system effectively so as to encourage transparency, better communication, and increased employee attachment. The findings are supported Thomas et al., (2009), effective and consistent communication from leaders is an important foundation in building work engagement, especially in organizations that are undergoing digital transformation. Korzynski, (2015), indicating that work engagement increases when leaders are actively involved in the organization's internal communication system.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study demonstrates that the use of artificial intelligence has not directly had a major impact on employee performance, based on data analysis from 225 workers working at KCP of state-owned banks in Surakarta City. The test results indicate that the notion that AI improves employee performance is not substantiated, despite the fact that the direction of influence is positive. Additionally, work attachment is positively but marginally impacted by artificial intelligence. This suggests that the use of AI has not been able to directly create work attachments, which are essentially relational and psychological. Nonetheless, the study's findings support the critical role that change leadership has in enhancing artificial intelligence's impact. The related hypothesis is said to be supported

since change leadership has been shown to positively and significantly attenuate the impact of AI on employee performance. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that change leadership significantly and favorably moderates the impact of AI on work attachment. All things considered, the results of this study demonstrate that the effectiveness of implementing artificial intelligence to enhance worker performance and work attachment depends not only on technological sophistication but also heavily on the leadership's ability to oversee the organizational adaptation process. By highlighting the fact that artificial intelligence is an external skill that does not instantly become an internal competence of the organization, this research theoretically enhances the Dynamic Capabilities Theory. The results demonstrate that, in the absence of appropriate managerial processes, the impact of AI on worker performance and work attachment likely to be minimal. The reconfiguration process is made possible by the dynamic capability of change leadership, which integrates and modifies AI into work processes and employee behavior. It is believed that work attachment and employee performance are internal competencies that can only be developed by adaptive change management. Practically speaking, our results verify that the effectiveness of AI adoption for KCP state-owned banks in Surakarta greatly depends on the caliber of change leadership in overseeing digital transformation in a sustainable way.

This study has a number of drawbacks, one of which is that it only looked at the state-owned banks' sub-branch offices in Surakarta that issue research permits; as a result, it cannot be broadly applied. Since these industries typically have more flexible organizational structures and comparatively simpler research licensing procedures than state-owned banking institutions, it is recommended that future research expand the research object to other industry sectors with a higher level of accessibility and openness of licensing, such as the manufacturing sector, retail companies, MSMEs, or the private service sector. Furthermore, the research employed cross-sectional data, which only recorded circumstances at a single moment in time. As a result, longitudinal design may be used in future studies to better understand the dynamics of shifting respondents' views and behavior over time.

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